

Thermal property analysis of epoxy based silver nanocomposites

V. Velmurugan*, R. Ramachandran and J. P. Raina

Center for Nanotechnology Research, VIT University, Vellore-632 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : vvelmurugan@vit.ac.in

Abstract : Thermal conductivity of polymer composites containing silver nanoparticles is investigated. Nano silver particles of an average size of 70 nm is synthesized by wet chemical method. Composite with different volume percentages of silver nanoparticles is made along with SU8 a well known epoxy based negative photoresist. To predict the thermal conductivity various theoretical models were studied. Experimental determination of thermal conductivity is done by Hot Wire technique. The relationship between the concentration of the nanoparticles and thermal conductivity is investigated. Jefferson, Witzell and Sibbitt theoretical model is found to be in good agreement with the experimental results.

Keywords : SU8, silver nano particle, thermal conductivity, epoxy.

Introduction

SU8 is a well known epoxy based negative tone photoresist designed for fabrication of MEMS, high aspect ratio structures, material for support, packaging etc. It is said to have multifunctional glycidyl ether derivatives of biphenol-A, triarylsulfonium, hexafluoroantimonate salt, photoacid generator and a thinning solvent¹. The epoxy based resist has been modified by several researchers to enhance its properties that results in different applications²⁻⁹. Enhanced thermal property of the epoxy can improve the lithography process as well as performance of sensors based on the thermal effects. In this work we tried to enhance the thermal property of the photopolymer with silver nanoparticles.

Experimental

0.5 mM of silver nitrate and 40 mg of polyvinylpyrrolidone were added into 100 ml of acetone. Then, 0.5 mM of sodium borohydride was added into the above solution and stirred for one hour at room temperature¹⁰. The change in the colour to brown indicates the formation of Ag nano colloid. TEM analysis (Fig. 1a) shows isolated silver nanoparticles of spherical morphology and some clustering due to the presence of the capping agent. The average particle size is ~70 nm and homogenous distribution of particles is observed. The XRD pattern of silver nano particles (Fig. 1b) shows four diffraction peaks corresponding to (111), (220), (220) and (311) planes of

face centered cubic phase as matched with the JCPDS card no. 89-3722. The broadening of the diffraction peaks are ascribed to very small crystalline size. Also, all the sharp diffraction peaks indicating that good crystallization of silver nanoparticles. No additional peaks in XRD reveals the high purity of silver particles¹¹. The crystallite size of ~15 nm have been calculated according to Scherrer's equation¹². The absorption spectrum of silver nano particle presented in Fig. 1c. The peak at 400 nm is characteristic for surface plasmon band for silver nanoparticles. The sharp plasmon band indicates the formation of silver particles at nanometer length scale. The small peak at higher energy, i.e. 275 nm is due to the formation of various types of silver ions such as Ag³⁺ and Ag²⁺ due to clustering¹³ or due to the presence of capping agent in silver solution. Silver nanoparticle is added to SU8 2050 (supplied by Microchem Inc.) in different volume percentages to form composites. The composites are coated on glass slides using a spin coater spun for 60 s and at a constant speed of 6500 rpm to get a uniform coating.

Results and discussion

Hot wire technique, a non steady state method¹⁴ is used measure the thermal conductivity. Heat is applied to a single wire for a time, t_h and temperature is monitored in that wire during heating and for an additional time

Fig. 1. (a) TEM image of silver nanoparticles, (b) XRD pattern of silver nanoparticle and (c) UV-Vis absorbance spectrum of silver nano solution.

equal to t_h after heating. The temperature during heating, temperature during cooling and the thermal conductivity is computed from eqs. (1), (2) and (3) respectively.

$$T = m_0 + m_2 t + m_3 \ln(t) \quad (1)$$

$$T = m_0 + m_2 t + m_3 \ln \left[\frac{t}{(t-t_h)} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$k = \frac{q}{4\pi m_3} \quad (3)$$

m_0 is the ambient temperature during heating, m_2 is the rate of background temperature drift, m_3 is the slope of a line relating temperature rise to logarithm of temperature, q is the heat input.

Relationship between thermal conductivity of composite and concentration of silver nanoparticles :

Several mathematical models were proposed¹⁴ to predict the thermal conductivity of polymers and composites. Majority of the models depends on the volume fraction of the nanoparticles, formation of two or single phase system, orientation, type of packing and geometric shapes. All the experimental values fall within the two basic models known as series and parallel models.

In this work we considered the following models,

- (i) Series model (eq. (4)) – This model assumes that there is no contact between the particles and the conduction is confined to that region¹⁴. Most of the models are the derivatives of series model.

$$k_e = (1 - \phi)k_c + \phi k_d \quad (4)$$

- (ii) Geometric mean model (eq. (5))

$$k_e = k_d^\phi + k_c^{(1-\phi)} \quad (5)$$

- (iii) Jefferson, Witzell and Sibbitt theoretical model (eq. (6)) – assumes that the particles are spherical in nature and the thermal conductivity is a derivative of series-parallel equivalent model¹⁵.

$$k_e = k_c \left[1 - \frac{\pi}{4(1+2n)^2} \right] + \frac{\pi}{4(1+2n)^2} \left[\frac{(0.5+n)k_d k_c}{0.5k_c + nk_d} \right] \quad (6)$$

where

$$n = 0.403\phi^{-1/3} - 0.5$$

$$k_d = k_d k_c \left[\frac{2k_d}{(k_d - k_c)^2} \ln \frac{k_d}{k_c} - \frac{2}{(k_d - k_c)} \right] \quad (7)$$

- (iv) Lewis and Nielsen semi-theoretical model (eq. (8)) considers the shape and the orientation of the particles¹⁴.

$$k_e = k_c \left[\frac{1 + AB\phi}{1 - A\phi} \right] \quad (8)$$

$A = 1.50$ for particles of spherical nature¹⁵ and the heat flow is in any directions.

$$B = \frac{\frac{k_d}{k_c} - 1}{\frac{k_d}{k_c} + A}$$

$$\phi = 1 + \left(\frac{1 - \phi_m}{\phi_m^2} \right) \phi \quad (9)$$

$\phi_m = 0.601$ for spherical particles arranged randomly (Packing factor). k_c – Thermal conductivity of SU8. k_d – Thermal conductivity of silver nanoparticles. k_e – Thermal conductivity of composite. ϕ – Volume fraction of discrete phase.

KD2 Pro thermal properties analyzer supplied by Decagon Devices, Inc., USA is used to measure the thermal conductivity. The stainless steel wire is completely immersed into the polymer composite. The measurement procedure is based on ASTM D5334 and IEEE 442-1981 standards. For calibration of the wire, we measured the thermal conductivity of glycerin. The measured value is $0.282 \text{ Wm}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ with an error of 2.82% that is in agreement with the literatures. During the measurement the temperature of the surrounding is kept constant to minimize the error. On an average the error is found to be 2.275%. A comparison of the experimental values of the thermal conductivity and the results of the predicted values by various models as described earlier is presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Thermal conductivity of the composites as a function of the volume percentage of silver nanoparticles.

The graph shows that the predictions by the geometric mean model and Lewis Nielsen semi-theoretical model deviate from the experimental values. Lewis Nielsen model shows a rapid increase in the thermal conductivity after 30% in the silver nanoparticle content due to the presence of packing factor in the equation¹⁴. But on the other hand Jefferson, Witzell and Sibbitt theoretical model holds good even upto 70% of nanosilver in the composites.

Conclusion

Silver nanoparticles were synthesized and epoxy based composites were made. The thermal conductivity of those composites containing silver nanoparticles are measured by hot wire technique. Well established mathematical models were used to predict the thermal conductivity. The prediction by Jefferson, Witzell and Sibbitt theoretical model – a derivative of serial and parallel thermal conductivity matches the experimental values.

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